

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN INTERNAL ORGANS DURING CHRONIC ALCOHOL INTOXICATION (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT: Chronic alcohol intoxication remains one of the leading medical and social problems of our time, causing high morbidity, disability, and premature mortality. The purpose of this review was to systematize modern literature data on the pathomorphological and pathogenetic mechanisms of internal organ damage during prolonged exposure to ethanol. The review analyzed data reflecting the multi-organ nature of alcoholism involving the central nervous system, liver, cardiovascular, bronchopulmonary, pancreatic, and reproductive systems. It has been shown that the direct cytotoxic effect of ethanol and acetaldehyde, microcirculatory disorders, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, immune dysregulation, and neuroendocrine disorders play a key role in the formation of alcohol-associated pathology. It has been established that in the early stages of alcoholic damage, structural and functional changes can be reversible, while continued alcoholism leads to the progression of dystrophic, inflammatory, and fibrous processes with the development of irreversible organ failure. Special attention has been paid to the genotoxic and mutagenic effects of alcohol, which pose a threat not only to the individual but also to the health of subsequent generations. A conclusion was made about the need for a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach to the prevention, early diagnosis, and treatment of chronic alcohol intoxication.

Keywords: Chronic alcohol intoxication, alcohol disease, pathomorphology, multiple organ involvement, ethanol, acetaldehyde.

ПАТОМОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ АЛКОГОЛЬНОЙ ИНТОКСИКАЦИИ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

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АННОТАЦИЯ: Хроническая алкогольная интоксикация остаётся одной из ведущих медико-социальных проблем современности, обуславливая высокую заболеваемость, инвалидизацию и преждевременную смертность. Целью настоящего обзора явилась

систематизация современных литературных данных о патоморфологических и патогенетических механизмах поражения внутренних органов при длительном воздействии этанола. В обзоре проанализированы данные, отражающие многоорганный характер алкогольной болезни с вовлечением центральной нервной системы, печени, сердечно-сосудистой, бронхолёгочной, панкреатической и репродуктивной систем. Показано, что ключевую роль в формировании алкоголь-ассоциированной патологии играют прямое цитотоксическое действие этанола и ацетальдегида, микроциркуляторные расстройства, оксидативный стресс, митохондриальная дисфункция, иммунная дисрегуляция и нейроэндокринные нарушения. Установлено, что на ранних этапах алкогольного поражения возможна обратимость структурно-функциональных изменений, тогда как продолжение алкоголизации приводит к прогрессированию дистрофических, воспалительных и фиброзных процессов с развитием необратимой органной недостаточности. Особое внимание уделено генотоксическим и мутагенным эффектам алкоголя, представляющим угрозу не только для индивидуума, но и для здоровья последующих поколений. Сделан вывод о необходимости комплексного междисциплинарного подхода к профилактике, ранней диагностике и лечению хронической алкогольной интоксикации.

Ключевые слова: хроническая алкогольная интоксикация, алкогольная болезнь, патоморфология, многоорганное поражение, этанол, ацетальдегид.

SURUNKALI ALKOGOLDAN ZAHARLANISHDA ICHKI A'ZOLARNING PATOMORFOLOGIK VA FUNKSIONAL O'ZGARISHLARI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

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Annotatsiya: Surunkali alkogol intoksikatsiyasi yuqori kasallanish, nogironlik va erta o'limni keltirib chiqaradigan zamonaviy yetakchi tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammolardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu sharhning maqsadi etanolning uzoq muddatli ta'sirida ichki a'zolar shikastlanishining patomorfologik va patogenetik mexanizmlari haqidagi zamonaviy adabiyot ma'lumotlarini tizimlashtirishdan iborat. Sharhda markaziy asab tizimi, jigar, yurak-qon tomir, bronx-o'pka, oshqozon osti bezi va reproduktiv tizimlarni o'z ichiga olgan alkogol kasalligining ko'p a'zoli tabiatini aks ettiruvchi ma'lumotlar tahlil qilingan. Alkogol bilan bog'liq patologiyaning shakllanishida etanol va atsetaldegidning bevosita sitotoksik ta'siri, mikrotsirkulyator buzilishlar, oksidativ stress, mitoxondrial disfunktsiya, immun disregulyatsiya va neyroendokrin buzilishlar asosiy rol o'ynashi ko'rsatilgan. Alkogoldan zararlanishning dastlabki bosqichlarida struktur-funksional o'zgarishlar qaytar bo'lishi mumkinligi, alkogolizatsiyaning davom etishi esa qaytarib bo'lmaydigan organ yetishmovchiligi rivojlanishi bilan distrofik, yallig'lanish va fibroz jarayonlarning kuchayishiga olib kelishi aniqlangan. Alkogolning genotoksik va mutagen ta'siriga alohida e'tibor qaratildi, bu nafaqat shaxsga, balki keyingi avlodlar salomatligiga ham xavf tug'diradi. Surunkali alkogol intoksikatsiyasining oldini olish, erta tashxislash va davolashga kompleks fanlararo yondashuv zarur degan xulosaga kelingan.

Kalit so'zlar: surunkali alkogol intoksikatsiyasi, alkogol kasalligi, patomorfologiyasi, ko'p a'zoli zararlanish, etanol, atsetaldegid.

Introduction. Chronic alcohol intoxication has remained one of the most significant medical and social problems for many decades, having a pronounced negative impact on public health and demographic indicators worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, alcohol abuse is the cause of more than 200 diseases and pathological conditions and is associated with a high level of premature mortality [1,2]. Prolonged systemic use of ethanol poses a particular danger, leading to the formation of multiple organ pathologies with irreversible structural and functional changes in internal organs.

In modern medicine, the concept of alcoholism as a universal, stage-by-stage, and progressive process, based on the direct toxic effects of ethanol and its metabolites, primarily acetaldehyde, as well as secondary metabolic, vascular, immune, and neuroendocrine disorders, is becoming increasingly established [3-5]. A characteristic feature of alcoholism is the systemic nature of the lesions, in which pathological changes develop simultaneously or sequentially in the central nervous system, liver, heart, lungs, pancreas, and reproductive system organs.

The central nervous system is one of the most vulnerable targets of chronic alcohol intoxication. Alcoholic encephalopathy is formed as a result of the neurotoxic effect of ethanol, disruption of energy metabolism in neurons, and deficiency of B vitamins, leading to dystrophic, atrophic, and necrotic changes in the brain substance [6,7]. Developing cognitive, motor, and behavioral disorders significantly reduce patients' quality of life and contribute to social maladjustment.

The liver, being the main organ of alcohol metabolism, is most pronouncedly damaged. Alcoholic liver disease includes a spectrum of morphological changes from fatty degeneration to alcoholic hepatitis and cirrhosis, reflecting the staged progression of the pathological process [8-10]. At the same time, it has been established that in the early stages, the lesions are reversible, while continued alcoholism leads to irreversible structural changes and liver failure.

Cardiovascular complications of chronic alcoholism are represented by alcoholic cardiomyopathy, rhythm disturbances, and microcirculatory disorders, which are one of the leading causes of sudden death in individuals who abuse alcohol [11,12]. The toxic effect of ethanol on the myocardium is accompanied by cardiomyocyte dystrophy, fibrosis, and a decrease in the heart's contractile capacity.

No less significant changes develop in the bronchopulmonary system, where alcohol disrupts mucociliary clearance, reduces surfactant production, and suppresses immune defense, contributing to the severe and prolonged course of respiratory infectious-inflammatory diseases [13,14]. The pancreas is also characterized by high sensitivity to alcohol, which clinically manifests as the development of acute and chronic pancreatitis, accompanied by pronounced morphological lesions of the acinar apparatus [15].

Reproductive system lesions occupy a special place in the structure of alcohol-associated pathology. Chronic alcohol intoxication leads to a decrease in the hormonal activity of gonads, disruption of spermatogenesis, the development of infertility, and has a mutagenic effect on reproductive cells, which increases the risk of congenital anomalies in offspring [16-18].

In connection with the above, a comprehensive analysis of the pathomorphological and pathogenetic aspects of internal organ damage in chronic alcohol intoxication is of significant scientific and practical interest. Summarizing the literature data allows for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms

of alcohol damage, identifying key targets for prevention and early intervention, and justifying the need to abstain from alcohol as an effective measure to prevent multiple organ pathologies.

The ongoing study of alcohol-associated lesions of internal organs is due not only to the high prevalence of chronic alcoholism but also to the significant clinical and pathogenetic polymorphism of the developing changes. Despite a large number of studies devoted to individual aspects of alcohol disease, the concept of the unity of pathogenetic mechanisms underlying multi-organ damage and their morphological reflection at various stages of intoxication remains insufficiently systematized to this day [19-21].

Of particular importance in the development of alcohol-induced pathology is the disruption of microcirculation, which is considered a universal link in tissue damage. Chronic exposure to ethanol leads to endothelial dysfunction, increased vascular wall permeability, activation of thrombus formation, and tissue hypoxia, exacerbating dystrophic and necrotic processes in parenchymal organs [22,23]. These changes create a morphological basis for the formation of fibrosis, sclerosis, and organ failure.

In recent years, researchers' attention has been focused on the role of oxidative stress and free radical damage to cell membranes in the pathogenesis of alcoholism. The activation of lipid peroxidation processes under the influence of acetaldehyde leads to damage to the mitochondrial apparatus of cells, disruption of energy metabolism, and induction of apoptosis, which is confirmed by morphological signs of cellular dystrophy and necrosis in various organs [24-26].

An equally important pathogenetic factor is the disruption of immune regulation. Chronic alcohol intoxication is accompanied by the suppression of cellular and humoral immunity, a change in the cytokine profile, and the formation of autoimmune reactions, which contributes to the chronicity of inflammatory processes and a decrease in the reparative potential of tissues [27,28]. Immune mechanisms are especially pronounced in alcoholic liver and myocardial disease, where persistent inflammatory infiltrates and progressive fibrosis are detected.

The genotoxic and mutagenic effects of ethanol and its metabolites deserve special attention. The accumulated data indicate alcohol's ability to cause DNA damage, disrupt reparation processes and epigenetic regulation, which is of fundamental importance for understanding the mechanisms of carcinogenesis and hereditary transmission of pathological changes [29-31]. In this context, alcohol intoxication is considered not only as an individual risk factor but also as a potential threat to the health of subsequent generations.

Thus, the need for a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach to studying chronic alcohol intoxication is due to the multi-level nature of pathogenetic mechanisms and the versatility of morphological manifestations of internal organ damage. This literature review is aimed at systematizing modern data on structural and functional changes in organs and tissues during the chronic effects of alcohol, identifying the key links in the pathogenesis, and substantiating preventive and clinical-diagnostic strategies aimed at reducing the burden of alcohol-associated pathology.

Conclusion: The analysis of modern literature convincingly demonstrates that chronic alcohol intoxication represents a complex, multi-stage, and progressive pathological process characterized by systemic involvement of vital organs and tissues. The damaging effects of ethanol and its toxic metabolites are realized through a combination of direct cytotoxic action, metabolic disturbances, microcirculatory disorders, oxidative stress, immune dysregulation, and neuroendocrine imbalance, which together determine the universality and severity of alcohol-associated organ damage.

Structural and functional alterations of the central nervous system, liver, cardiovascular, bronchopulmonary, pancreatic, and reproductive systems develop in a stereotypical sequence and show a clear dependence on the duration and intensity of alcohol exposure. At early stages, a number of alcohol-induced changes are potentially reversible; however, continued alcohol consumption leads to progressive dystrophic, inflammatory, and fibrotic processes with the formation of irreversible organ failure and an increased risk of premature mortality.

The reviewed data highlight the key pathogenetic role of microcirculatory impairment, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and immune imbalance as universal mechanisms underlying multi-organ damage in chronic alcoholism. Particular attention should be paid to the genotoxic and mutagenic effects of ethanol, which extend the consequences of alcohol abuse beyond the individual level and pose a threat to the health of future generations.

The systematization of current scientific evidence emphasizes the necessity of an integrated and interdisciplinary approach to the study of chronic alcohol intoxication, combining morphological, biochemical, immunological, and clinical perspectives. Such an approach is essential for the development of effective preventive strategies, early diagnostic criteria, and pathogenetically substantiated therapeutic interventions aimed at reducing the burden of alcohol-associated diseases.

In conclusion, timely identification of alcohol-induced organ damage and complete abstinence from alcohol remain the most effective measures to prevent the progression of multiple organ pathology. Further research should focus on clarifying the molecular mechanisms of alcohol toxicity, identifying early biomarkers of tissue damage, and evaluating long-term outcomes of preventive and therapeutic strategies in patients with chronic alcohol intoxication.

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